

Understanding of Children's Privacy Rights Protection in Sharenting Practice on Social Media

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ABSTRACT

Sharenting is a new phenomenon resulting from the increased activity of social media users. Sharenting is an activity to share children's activities and lives uploaded on social media. Sharenting activities negatively impact children because all types of activities uploaded on social media are not with the children's approval. The research objective is to examine parents' understanding of violations and protection of children's privacy in sharenting practices on social media and to investigate violations committed by parents in sharenting activities. This research employed a descriptive qualitative method with parent respondents who actively used Instagram social media and worked as local Purwakarta celebgrams. Data collection used observation and interviews and was analyzed by data reduction, presentation, and verification. The research results revealed that sharenting activities were often carried out by parents and were published on the Instagram social media platform for various reasons and motives. The sharenting practice was sharing videos and photos of daily life and the growth and development of children periodically. Sharenting activities were also carried out because parents did not understand the negative impact on children's privacy and lacked insight into government regulations on children's privacy rights violations.

INTRODUCTION

The digital era is a period of rapid information and communication technology development as a technical tool for processing and manipulating information. Information can be spread without boundaries through internet media, a product of the digital era. Internet use in parts of the world is massive and comprehensive. Based on survey results, Asosiasi Penyelenggara Jasa Internet Indonesia (APJII) internet users in Indonesia reached 215.63 million people in 2022-2023. This number has increased compared to the previous period, i.e., 210.03 million users. It denotes that the number of internet users reaches 78.19% of the total population of Indonesian people, i.e., 275.77 million people.

Access to internet use in Indonesia is very easy to obtain, supported by the public's openness and acceptance in receiving information, this is inseparable from the rapid development of cellular telephones which are widely used by the public as released by Indonesian telecommunications statistics in 2021, recorded at 90.54% of households. In Indonesia you have at least one cell phone number.

Internet use in Indonesia cannot be separated from the domain of social media use. Popular social media Indonesians use include Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, Twitter, and YouTube. The use of social media is carried out by Indonesian people using the internet network for an average of three hours and fourteen minutes daily. Additionally, the use of social media in Indonesia reaches 170 million people, or 61.8% of the Indonesian population (Permanasari & Sirait 2021).

Activities using social media are carried out by various groups and generations. This includes children, youth and the elderly. In the domain of increased use of social media by parents raises a new phenomenon called sharenting. Sharenting is an activity of publishing data in the form of photos, videos uploaded on social media. Sharenting is also the behavior of parents to share various life activities of their children online. Manifestations of parental behavior can be in the form of sharing daily information, child development which is described in detail in the form of photos, personal data, videos on social media.

On the other side, the behavior of sharing children's personal information and data is an activity that has a harmful impact on children, especially minors. Nowadays, many cases are affected by sharenting behavior, such as bullying, pedophilia, and sexual violence against children. In addition, this sharenting activity is also considered to violate the children's privacy because they take actions sharing information about children without the children's consent (Brosch:2018). However, many parents still do not believe that sharing activities can have negative impacts. Parents believe that sharenting activities will not risk causing harm to the children, as one of the reasons parents commit sharenting activities is because they do not know about the threats of the online environment. According to Dwiarsianti (2022) The low awareness of parents in knowing the positive and negative impacts of sharing activities is the main cause of parents doing sharenting. The research results implied that many

parents still uploaded their children's photos, their children's habits, and things that should not be shown to the public without considering the impacts on the child's privacy in the future.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Legal Umbrella for Children's Rights and Privacy The children's need for privacy protection is an essential matter that parents must consider. Privacy is all information related to a person's honor without exception, which belongs to everyone, such as infants, children, adolescents, and adults. Likewise, in childhood, the right to privacy should be studied together. In this case, several theories and legal bases exist behind children's privacy rights under international and national laws.

In terms of the provisions of international rules, discussion of privacy rights and personal data have been discussed periodically. The child's data is spread out and can be accessed by other people, triggering the vulnerability of the free dissemination of information. Dissemination of personal data, identity, photos, videos, hobbies, and daily activities will cause other people to identify the child's identity and habits.

This results in a susceptible situation for children's freedom rights violations. Hence, in 1948, several UN member states created the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR). Generally, the UDHR protects the rights of every human being. The subject intended in this declaration is not limited by age; thus, it applies universally. This rule includes the right to privacy as a human right in Article 12, which states:

"No one shall be subjected to arbitrary interference with his privacy, family, home or correspondence, nor to attacks upon his honor and reputation. Everyone has the right to the protection of the law against such interference or attacks".

This article becomes a legal umbrella (protection) in protecting a person's rights and privacy that privacy is information that contains a person's integrity and honor. Everyone has the right to get legal protection if there is interference from other people. Furthermore, the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) Council Recommendation on the Protection of Children Online 2012 is an international organization that aims to solve social, economic, and environmental issues. Moreover, the OECD Council protects children's rights online by involving several elements of society, such as stakeholder and parental policies. Meanwhile, the principles inscribed are empowerment, proportionality, fundamental values, and flexibility. This organization aims to protect children and minimize the risk of child crime online.

Several organizations above that initiated privacy rights in the digital world emerged several new rules, such as the Asia Pacific Economic Co-operation (APEC) Privacy Framework 2015, which specifically regulates information protection systems to protect personal data and one's privacy. Personal information in this framework is any information that can be

employed to identify an individual. In addition, information that, combined with other information, will identify the person, e.g., metadata. Therefore, it will be easy for everyone to analyze a person's habits and daily life.

The legal basis in Indonesia regarding the privacy and protection of children's personal data is stated in the Indonesian state constitution Article 28 G paragraph (1), which mentions, "Everyone has the right to protection of himself/herself, family, honor, dignity, and property under his control, as well as the right to feel safe and protected from threats of fear to do or not do something that is a human right". Article 28 G paragraph (1) states that the category of every person is an elaboration of all members of society without exception. Children are part of every person whose rights and privacy are protected, and it seeks to protect the rights of all children of the nation.

In addition, the legal basis for child protection is contained in Law Number 23 of 2002 on Child Protection, which was renewed by Law Number 35 of 2014 concerning Amendments to Law Number 23 of 2002 on Child Protection. Furthermore, to protect children when they use the internet, the Government of Indonesia has established Law Number 11 of 2008 concerning Information and Electronic Transactions, which was amended by Law Number 19 of 2016 concerning Amendments to Law Number 11 of 2008 on Electronic Information and Transactions, Ministry of Communication and Informatics Regulation Number 20 of 2016 on Protection of Personal Data, and Government Regulation Number 43 of 2017 on Implementation of Restitution for Children who Become Victims of Crime as an effort to protect, return, and fulfill the rights of children who are victims of crime. Article 26, Paragraph 1 of the Electronic Information and Transaction Law states that privacy protection, a personal right, is regulated by using information technology. This article discusses the right to enjoy a private life and be free from various forms of interference, the right to communicate with others, and the right to monitor access to information and one's life.

The term 'sharenting' is a combination of the two words share and parenting, referring to the trend in cyberspace that parents do when sharing detailed information about their children on social media (Dwiarsianti: 2022). The term sharenting first appeared on the internet in 2013, and since then, the phenomenon has grown in popularity until finally, it has been used in scientific publications since 2015. Sharenting is a new phenomenon caused by the large use of social media. Sharenting activity is a parent's behavior in posting photos, videos, personal data, and children's daily lives on social media (Hidayati: 2023).

A similar statement was conveyed by the researcher, who discovered that sharenting was more likely to be committed by mothers with younger children because older children would have a stronger say in what things of themselves their parents are allowed to share online. The development of the sharenting trend has also been triggered by the growing trend of female celebrities or influencers (Archer: 2019) . The celebgram is someone who has many followers on Instagram and does not have to come from celebrities. These

ordinary people can interact with the wider public, garnering likes, comments, shares, and thousands of followers on social media who are willing to follow.

METHODS

This research employed a descriptive qualitative method with data collection techniques through interviews, observation, and notes. Data were analyzed by coding the results of the interviews and observation notes, which were analyzed by data reduction, data presentation, and verification. Research respondents consisted of parents whose underage children worked as celebgrams. In this case, the selected parents actively use Instagram social media. Respondent criteria were selected based on the initial observations of four parents whose Instagram followers are more than 10 thousand followers. In their daily lives, they frequently post daily activities with their children. It was the background for researchers to explore and analyze parents' understanding of children's privacy and sharenting.

RESULTS

Sharenting Activities on Social Media

Discussion of sharenting on social media is a phenomenon of rapid technological sophistication which has an impact on changes in various aspects of life such as social, economic, lifestyle and cultural changes. Sharenting activities are generally found in various flat forms of social media, as will be discussed, namely on Instagram social media. The respondents in this research were 4 mothers who worked as local Instagram celebrities in Purwakarta. Based on the results of observations, it was generally found that 4 parents who carried out sharenting activities consciously shared data in the form of their children's full names, photos and videos of their children on their Instagram feed. In this case, there are several categories of sharenting activities which will be illustrated in the following table.

Table 1. Parental Sharing Activities on Instagram

No	Category	Upload
1	Maternal pregnancy and child development	Instagram story and feed
2	Children's daily	Instagram story
3	Children's academic activities	Instagram story
4	Child endorsements	Instagram story and feed

Based on the results of observations and interviews, the activities of posting and disseminating children's lives consist of several categories of parental behavior on social media. Parents carry out online activities by consciously posting photos and videos of children in the form of prenatal and

post-natal child development, videos of children's daily activities and activities, children's academic activities while studying at home, as well as endorsements for children. Four parents (mothers) agreed that the activity of publishing children's activities was to provide information about their daily activities to followers of their parents' Instagram accounts in order to get lots of viewers and likes from their followers. They are of the opinion that the life of a celebrity does not escape the public's attention, so every form of daily life activity does not escape the spotlight of public consumption, including his personal and family life. According to them, being a celebgram must have its own characteristics and character in displaying self-image on Instagram social media. Self-image is formed through a sharenting activity that is routinely distributed to the public such as providing information on good parenting patterns to apply to their children so as to create the impression that the parenting style used is a role model for the public to follow. Self-image is also deliberately formed by regularly posting every activity, lifestyle, hobby, or self-interest through a picture and video on Instagram.

Based on the results of interview analysis and observation, the motives for carrying out sharenting activities vary. Some argue that sharenting activity is an activity to build self-image as an ideal young mother in the public eye. According to them, being a celebrity has flexible time which allows them to spend a lot of time with their families, especially with their children. This can inspire followers to become an ideal mother who is good at managing work and family. Self-image is formed based on personal reasons, one of which is to attract a large number of followers, likes and viewers on Instagram. The effect of increasing the number of viewers and likes in each post will have an impact on increasing the "engagement" rate, that is, from the increase in engagement, they can gain benefits such as the number of incoming endorsers. They can get this when the public likes every post, lifestyle, including liking their child's profile. In line with research conducted in other countries, many of the motives underlying the desire of parents to sharenting are based on self-pride to show their child's strengths to gain social recognition in the eyes of the public. Sharenting also involves parents' egos in fulfilling their own desires in order to gain approval from the public. Sharenting allows parents to compare themselves with other parents in terms of social status, life experience, and sense of pride. Sharenting can have positive and negative emotional impacts such as getting pleasant and disappointing comments from public comments on posts. For example, when parents share photos or stories about their children on social media, it allows them to connect with family or friends so that these posts become a form of existence on social media with the public (Udenze & Bode: 2020). Based on the findings, the motive behind sharenting activities is simply as a form of hobby to capture important moments in life. Such as sharing moments of pregnancy development through videos and photos is an important documentation that will one day be remembered by parents. Likewise with children's daily activities, children's academic activities, and children's growth and development diaries posted on Instagram will become separate documentation for children and parents. They consider Instagram to

be an eternal container to capture the important moments of their life compared to storing it in a personal hard drive which may one day be damaged.

DISCUSSION

Understanding Children's Privacy Rights in Terms of Law

Basically, children's rights to privacy have been regulated in several countries, including Indonesia. The interests of children to have their privacy rights protected are recognized in the legal and academic aspects. In the process of protecting children's privacy rights, it will be related to the involvement of parents and children because children do not participate in the decision-making process in a case, especially minors. Thus, parents act as controllers and controllers in the decision-making process for children (Handayani: 2021, Utomo:2022). According to Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 35 of 2014 Article 1 concerning Child Protection, every effort is made to guarantee and protect children and their rights so that they can live, grow, develop and participate optimally in accordance with their dignity, as well as receive protection from violence. and discrimination.

Article 26 of the ITE Law states that the use of any information via electronic media that concerns a person's personal data must be carried out with the consent of the person concerned. In protecting children's privacy rights, the parents represent to give consent in providing information about the child's personal data. Thus, the right to privacy is a person's right not to have their private life disturbed by other people. Privacy is a confidential and sensitive matter, so privacy must be protected and respected by the Government and fellow humans.

Based on the results of observations and interviews, parents do not yet understand the meaning of their children's right to privacy on social media. This is proven by the fact that parents' decision-making processes are still found in uploading all forms of children's activities and personal data. It was found that parents consciously uploaded photos and full names of their children on feeds and Instagram stories. Apart from that, in terms of the risks of sharenting related to children's privacy, 4 parents were proven to upload their children's daily activities repeatedly and upload locations where their children played and carried out academic activities at school. This shows that most parents do not understand which information about their children needs to be protected and does not need to be shown to the public. The activity of uploading the location of children's schools, homes and playgrounds is an act of oversharing which can have a negative impact on children (Adawiyah: 2021).

In studying sharenting, there will be a contradiction between the child's right to privacy and the parent's right to carry out the activities they need. In this case, parents will retain the right to express themselves as they wish. From a legal perspective, children do not have strong control over the information parents share about their children online. Apart from that, children cannot obtain the right to register for social media accounts because the applicable provisions on social media do not allow minors to register. Thus, from a legal perspective, children under the age of 13 do not have legal capacity so they

cannot make decisions about what information they can share online. Sarkadi et al (2020) conducted a survey of children aged 4-15 years in Australia regarding sharenting. in their research. This shows that parents do not have high awareness that their children's bodies need to be protected and should not be used for public consumption.

Based on the results of observations and interviews, there is still a lack of awareness of parents about the importance of free child growth and development without any interference from other parties. One way a child's healthy growth and development is influenced by external influences is the sense of security provided by parents and those around them. Children's privacy includes security in the space for children to move during daily activities, protecting children from all forms of crime arising from sharenting behavior such as pedophilia, sexual violence, data theft, exploitation, and others. In line with research (Fridha & Irawan, 2020) sharenting activities allow for the exploitation of children, such as the trend of celebrities trying to introduce their children through social media so that the public knows that these children have the status of celebrity children. This is not necessarily known by the wider community if parents who work as celebgrams are always consistent in sharing moments of growth and development, activities, and pictures of their children through social media. It can be concluded that children are under the control of their parents, because children become celebrities not because of their own will but because they are under the control of their parents.

Basically, children are under the control of parents who also have rights and obligations to fulfill the child's own rights. Article 26 of the IT Law states that the use of any information through electronic media concerning a person's personal data must be carried out with the consent of the person concerned. Consent is a condition for the use of a person's personal data, including children's personal data. Because the child is not yet an adult, the parents have the right to represent the child in giving this permission. However, if parents ignore the child's right to privacy, then the state in this case must step in as a protector of the child's rights. Children's participation in every decision is based on the consideration that children have the same rights as adults so that the development process that will occur in the future will not be affected by sharing activities carried out by parents.

Regarding violations of children's privacy, the ITE Law can be used. Any person whose rights to their personal data are violated can file a lawsuit for the losses incurred. A lawsuit can be based on the use of information via electronic media that concerns a person's personal data. As for the ITE Law, there is still a lot of confusion in the application process. In cases of violations of children's privacy, it is possible for anyone whose right to privacy and personal data has been violated to file a lawsuit for the losses caused.

However, the formula that states "every person" only applies to legal subjects who are competent according to the law is a legal principle that refers to the ability of individuals to act in their own legal capacity. This means that a person is deemed to have legal capacity or legal capacity to carry out legal

actions, such as filing a lawsuit or participating in legal proceedings, if they are considered legally competent. However, when a child becomes a victim, especially in the context of legislation governing child protection, legal regulations often recognize that children may not have the full legal capacities of adults. Therefore, in many jurisdictions, there are specific legal mechanisms that allow an adult, such as a parent or guardian, to act as a legal representative or protector of the child.

In cases where parents become lawbreakers against their own children, the situation becomes more complicated. Applying the article that applies to "everyone" may be difficult because parents are also legal subjects who should be subject to the law. In situations like this, the legal system may have to find alternative solutions, such as involving other parties as legal representatives or protectors for the child, or involving competent child protection agencies to handle the case.

It is important to note that legal capacity requirements and child protection mechanisms can vary between jurisdictions, and are often dependent on local laws and regulations. Therefore, in concrete cases, it will be very important to consult an experienced lawyer or legal expert to obtain legal advice appropriate to the jurisdiction and situation in question.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This research provides a very relevant description of the sharenting phenomenon and its impact on children's privacy. Sharenting has become a common activity on social media, but often parents are not aware of the potential risks associated with it. The following are some important points that can be drawn from the findings of this study:

1. **Extensive Internet Profile Exposure:** Sharenting can result in children's wide Internet profile exposure. Information, photos and videos about children that are shared online can be easily accessed by anyone, including unknown parties. This can endanger the child's privacy.
2. **Loss of Privacy:** Children who are regularly posted on social media by parents may have no control over their personal information. They may feel that their privacy has been violated and lose control over their online self-image.
3. **Possible Online Crime:** Information and images of children that are publicly shared can be used by irresponsible parties for malicious purposes, such as monitoring, kidnapping or other abuse. This is a serious risk that parents should consider.
4. **Effects on Children's Mental Health and Identity:** Too much online exposure can impact a child's mental health and identity development. Kids may feel burdened or pressured by the pressure to look perfect on social media.
5. **Protection of Children's Privacy Rights:** As parents, it is important to understand the importance of protecting children's privacy rights. This includes not sharing information that is too personal or images that may harm them in the future

Based on the results of the research, it was found that there were a lot of sharenting activities carried out by parents on social media which triggered crimes and harmed children's development. Therefore, it is hoped that readers will be able to understand the impact of sharing and have awareness in protecting children's privacy. In addition, the recommendation for future researchers is to dissect laws and regulations related to children's rights and privacy so as to provide solutions for weaknesses in the application of laws governing child privacy in Indonesia.

FURTHER STUDY

From the results of this research, it is hoped that it will make a significant contribution to the process of socializing the dangers of sharenting on the social media Instagram among parents who have professions as Instagram celebrities. However, this research still has many shortcomings and weaknesses, including not examining the positive impact of sharenting activities carried out by parents. Therefore, suggestions for future researchers are to discuss the comparison of the positive and negative impacts of sharenting activities. Apart from that, future researchers need to discuss the weaknesses and strengths of the legal umbrella in Indonesia regarding sharenting, so that sharenting cases that occur in society can be easily understood by those who have cases.

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